

FAILURE MODELLING OF IMPREGNATED FLAX YARNS FROM FIBRE AND INTERPHASE PROPERTIES

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1 Introduction

Increasing emphasis on environmentally friendly products and production has led to a growing interest in structural applications of natural fibre composites (NFCs). A well-developed understanding of their failure behavior can lead to improved failure models, and eventual structural applications.

Natural fibres are complex in structure [1], and display a large scatter in their mechanical properties. This complexity adds to the challenge of predicting the behavior of NFCs. To the authors' best knowledge, most failure analysis of NFCs has mostly been limited to experimental investigations and semi-empirical formulations, with some numerical studies on the interface between fibres or between fibres and matrix [2, 3].

In addition to fibre behavior, the properties of the interphase region are of utmost importance in understanding the deformation behavior of NFCs or any composite for that matter. Hence, a significant portion of this paper will be dedicated to modeling the failure behaviour of the interphase region. The key aims of this paper are to understand the failure behavior of the fibre and interphase components of a flax composite, and to use this understanding to analyse the failure of matrix-impregnated flax yarns.

In our research, we aim to test and model the properties of NFCs starting from the micro-scale. The micro-scale models in turn will feed into a more complex model which will be able to predict the properties of the composite at larger scales. Following this methodology, in this paper, we will test and model the properties of the fibre and interphase components, and then use these to obtain the properties of matrix-impregnated yarns.

2 Background

2.1. Fibre composition

Most of the early research into the structure and chemical compositions of natural fibres has in fact been carried out for wood fibres. From among the various proposed models for elastic fibre behavior [1, 4-7], one can draw out a generalized model as illustrated in Fig. 1. In this model, each fibre is composed of multiple layers referred to as middle lamellae (ML), P, S₁, S₂ and S₃, with a hollow lumen in the centre. The ML and P layers are often combined and referred to as combined middle lamellae (CML) [5].

Each layer is itself analogous to a unidirectional (UD) composite, with oriented cellulose microfibrils (CMF) embedded in a matrix of lignin and hemicellulose, and winding around the fibre axis in a helical manner. Fibres can then be considered as laminated composite cylinders, and composite laminate theory (CLT) can thus be applied to analyse their mechanical behavior.

The S₂ layer occupies 60-70% of the fibre volume [7, 8], and usually has CMFs with the steepest microfibril helix angle (MFA), due to which it has the most significant contribution to the longitudinal modulus. It is common to model the fibre modulus by applying a composite lamina treatment to the S₂ layer alone, and to calculate the variation in modulus with MFA of the CMFs in the S₂ layer, but we have considered the other layers also in our analyses.

2.2. Interphase behaviour

In most composites, a separate interphase layer exists between the fibre and matrix phases, either due to the fibres acting as crystal nucleation surfaces, or due to absorption of curing agents from

the matrix by the sizing agents present around the fibres.

Several techniques have been proposed to obtain the strength of the interphase region of composites, among which the microbond technique [9] is one of the more commonly used techniques due to two reasons – i) ease of preparation of the specimen, and ii) very small or no meniscus region as compared to disk-shaped specimens. The microbond test configuration is shown in Fig. 2, where a fibre is pulled upwards while a droplet surrounding it is restrained from moving up using a set of parallel blades or an annular ring. The angle ϕ made by the parallel blades with the axis of the fibre is called the blade/vice angle.

Over the years, several formulations have been proposed to model the interphase properties. These are of great use in grading/ranking of different composites, but since we are more interested in what could be a reasonable approximation of an absolute value, we will use a finite element (FE) model to obtain this value.

FE models usually consider the properties of the interphase layer as varying from the fibre surface to the matrix in a gradual manner, and different forms [10-12] have been used to represent this gradation. In this paper, we will consider exponential variation, linear variation and reciprocal variation, which in that same order can be expressed as:

$$E(x)_{interface} = A_1 + A_2 e^{-kx} \quad (1)$$

$$E(x)_{interface} = A_1 + rA_2 \quad (2)$$

$$E(x)_{interface} = \frac{A_1}{r - A_2} \quad (3)$$

where E represents the Young's modulus, A_1 , A_2 and k are constants, and r is the radial distance outward from the fibre surface, through the droplet. Density and Poisson's ratio can also be calculated using similar expressions. If we consider the interphase layer as beginning from the fibre surface, and extending till the matrix surface over a certain interphase thickness t , then the constants can be obtained by considering the fibre and matrix properties as boundary values.

3 Materials, characterization and methods

Unidirectional flax fabric of areal density 180 gsm and yarn linear density 41.7 tex was obtained from Libeco, Belgium, and Prime 20 epoxy resin was used as the matrix for the impregnated yarns. The properties of the Prime 20 resin, as supplied by the manufacturer, are listed in Table 1.

Optical microscopy was used to characterize fibre and yarn diameters, and to measure yarn helix angles. Material densities were measured using the Archimedes method with canola oil as the immersion medium.

3.1. Fibre properties

3.1.1 Single fibre tensile tests

A sample of fibres was separated from fabric yarns, and mounted on paper frames with square cutouts in the middle. For each specimen, a single fibre was positioned at the centre of these paper frames, and bonded to the paper using two droplets of epoxy. These droplets were placed right at the top and bottom edges, respectively, of the square cut-out, such that the tested gauge length was 25 mm. Fibre diameters were measured at six places along the tested length of the fibre using an optical microscope, and the average value was used to calculate properties. The single fibre tensile tests (SFTTs) were performed at a rate of 1 mm/min using an Instron 5567 UTM. Specimens were not pre-loaded before the commencement of data recording.

3.1.2 Weibull distribution fitting

Two-parameter Weibull distributions were used to approximate the distribution of the Young's modulus and strength values. In order to determine whether the Young's modulus and strength values for the tested fibres could be fit to Weibull distributions, the values from each set of properties (either modulus or strength) were first plotted on a Weibull plot (Fig. 3). This is a type of Q-Q plot of the cumulative distribution $\hat{F}(x)$, with $\ln(-\ln(1 - \hat{F}(x)))$ plotted against $\ln(x)$, where x is the data set for which the distribution is required. For the data to follow a Weibull distribution, the points on the Weibull plot should lie approximately along a straight line. In such a case, the parameters for the distribution (scale and shape parameters α and β) can be obtained from the slope and intercept of the straight line fits.

3.1.3 Fibre modulus analytical model

The longitudinal and transverse moduli of flax fibres were modelled by considering them as analogous to laminated composites. As illustrated in Fig. 1, each fibre was assumed to be composed of four layers - CML, S₁, S₂ and S₃. Since the S₂ layer constitutes a majority of the fibre volume, and since it has the steepest MFA, some models ignore the contribution of the other layers in the analysis of fibre longitudinal modulus. In this study, we modelled the longitudinal and transverse moduli of the fibre, with a) only the S₂ layer, and b) an assembly of the four layers. For case b, two different sets of relative thicknesses for the layers were considered – one put forward by Astley [13] and referred to as ASM1, and another proposed by Gassan [14] and referred to as ASM2. The relative thicknesses are as given in Table 2.

The lamina was assumed to be composed of CMF in a matrix of lignin and hemicellulose, and the properties for the components were combined from a range of sources [1, 5, 7, 15].

Rule of mixtures was used to calculate the longitudinal properties of the lamina corresponding to the different layers, and modified Halpin-Tsai equations were used to calculate the transverse properties. The constitutions of the different layers as reported by Harrington et al. [5] were used for the calculations. Two different volume fractions of CMF in the S₂ layer were considered: 0.65 and 0.7, while the volume fractions of the CML, S₁ and S₃ layers were held constant. The engineering stiffness matrix for the lamina was calculated using the CLT equation:

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_{xx}} & \frac{-\nu_{yx}}{E_{yy}} & 0 \\ \frac{-\nu_{xy}}{E_{xx}} & \frac{1}{E_{yy}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{xy}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where S is the compliance matrix (inverse of stiffness matrix), E_{xx} , E_{yy} and G_{xy} are the longitudinal, transverse and shear moduli, and ν_{xy} and ν_{yx} are the in-plane Poisson ratios.

The rotated stiffness matrices for the UD lamina over a possible range of helix angles between 2°-30° [6, 16] were calculated using the CLT, and

the longitudinal modulus corresponding to loading the lamina at an angle was calculated for each angle from the corresponding compliance matrices.

3.2. Interphase properties

3.2.1 Microbond tests

The microbond technique was used to characterize the flax/epoxy system under consideration, using parallel blades to restrict the droplet. Specimen preparation consisted of applying a single droplet of epoxy resin onto a single flax fibre.

3.2.2 Micromechanical analysis

In order to determine a nominal fibre-matrix interfacial shear stress (IFSS) value, τ , Miller [9] proposed an assumption of uniform shear stress over the entire length of the interface as

$$\tau = \frac{P}{\pi D l} \quad (5)$$

where P is the fibre pullout load, D is the diameter of the fibre, and l is the length of the fibre embedded in the matrix (Fig. 2). The same formula can be used to calculate frictional shear stress once the droplet is completely debonded, replacing P with the load due to friction.

This analysis is, of course a simplification of the loading case, and assumes that the entire load applied acts over the surface of a cylinder surrounding the fibre. The values obtained from this analysis will be compared to numerical simulations of the microbond test.

3.2.3 Microbond test simulation

Numerical models were set up to simulate the microdroplet test used to determine fibre-matrix interfacial shear strength (IFSS). As noted by Ash et al. [17], the shape of a droplet can vary considerably from that of circular arc or ellipse approximations, and they suggest using Carroll's fitting method [18] which has been specifically developed for drop-on-fibre systems. Hence, the profile of the droplet for which simulation was performed was fitted to arc, ellipse and Carroll's shapes, and the best fit was selected to generate the geometry for meshing.

It is somewhat common to use an axisymmetric model to simplify the cost of analyzing the microbond test [11, 17, 19], however,

as pointed out by Ash et al. [17], this can only directly relate to an experiment where an annular ring is used to restrain the droplet, instead of parallel vice grips. In this model, a quarter of the specimen was used with symmetry conditions, and one of the parallel vice grips was represented by a solid block made of steel. Surface-to-surface contact interaction was enabled between the outer surface of the droplet and the block. The ABAQUS explicit solver was used for the solution with mass scaling enabled to reduce the computational cost. Adaptive meshing with frequent remeshing was employed to deal with the large distortion anticipated.

Specific material models were used to control the mechanical behavior of the matrix and interphase, via the user material (VUMAT) interface available in ABAQUS. Failed elements were deleted from the FE model by setting a variable to control element deletion. The value of this variable was modified within the VUMAT subroutines.

3.3 Impregnated yarn failure

3.3.1 Testing

Warp yarns were extracted from the unidirectional fabric, dried in a vacuum oven for more than 12 hours, individually impregnated with epoxy resin, and cured at 70°C. The diameter of the impregnated yarns was also calculated from the average of six readings along the tested length.

Drum grips were used to fix these yarns within the frame of the Instron 5567 UTM, and they were tested to failure in the longitudinal direction at a rate of 5 mm/min. Again the specimens were not loaded before the start of data recording.

3.3.2 Simulation

The impregnated yarn model was constructed with fibres winding helically around the yarn axis. A thin layer corresponding to the interface was added around each fibre, and all the fibres and interface layers were then embedded in a matrix cylinder.

Strengths and stiffness values were assigned to the fibres by using a random number generator in conjunction with the Weibull distribution parameters obtained for modulus and strength (Fig. 4). The elements at the fibre-matrix interface (Fig. 5, dark region around fibres) were assigned the same stiffness and strength properties as the interface elements used in the microdroplet simulation.

In the experiments, as there was no preload, a knee can be observed. Replication of this behavior in the simulation is somewhat complicated since the geometry needs to be generated taking into account the slack due to gravity. It has been assumed that the slack does not affect the loaded elastic stiffness and strength properties.

4 Results and discussion

As per the strategy outlined earlier, a hierarchical approach was applied - obtaining material properties at the micro-scale, linking them to models, and then feeding these micro-scale properties into a larger scale model. Fibre properties have been determined first, fit to Weibull distributions, and compared to predictions using CLT theory. The fibre properties have then been used in simulations of the microbond test performed to determine properties of the interphase. The properties of the fibre and the interphase were then used to model the failure of matrix-impregnated flax yarns.

4.1 Fibre properties

4.1.1 SFTT data and Weibull fits

When the set of modulus values and strength values were plotted on separate Weibull plots, most of the points lay along a straight line for both the modulus and strength values except for a few outliers (as shown in Fig. 3). This means that these sets of values can be reasonably fit to Weibull distributions. The parameters for the distribution (scale and shape parameters) were obtained from the slope and intercept of the straight line fits in Figs. 3a and 3b.

The histograms for the fibre modulus and strength values were plotted in Fig. 4, and the values predicted by the Weibull distributions were overlaid on the histograms.

4.1.2 Fibre modulus analytical model

The longitudinal moduli predicted by the different laminate layup models are shown in Fig. 8a. The values for the UD lamina used to calculate the oblique moduli are given in Table 3.

The histogram of the fibre modulus values shows that the majority of the fibres (over 93%) possess a longitudinal modulus in the 10-50 GPa range. For

the upper limit of 50 GPa in this range, the corresponding S_2 layer MFAs vary between 2° - 9° for the various models, while for the lower limit of 10 GPa, the S_2 MFAs lie between 20° - 30° . This range of MFA value between 2° - 30° is in good agreement with experimentally reported values [6, 7, 16]. This shows that a low MFA leads to high longitudinal modulus of the fibres.

The same models used to calculate the longitudinal modulus values were also used for transverse modulus calculations. The predicted variation in transverse modulus with MFA is quite different from that of the longitudinal modulus – the values remain relatively constant in the MFA range 0° - 6° , and then rapidly decreases with increasing MFA.

4.2 Interface properties

4.2.1 Microbond tests and micromechanical analysis

Tests were performed on flax/epoxy microbond specimens, and the results are shown in Fig. 7. The typical behaviour of debonding followed by a drop in load and frictional loading after failure of the interface can be observed. Nominal interfacial shear stresses and frictional shear stresses were calculated using Equation 5.

4.2.2 Microbond test simulation

The geometry of specimen 3 (Fig. 8) has been studied, and fit using arc and ellipse, and Carroll's equations were used to approximate the droplet profile. There is almost no perceptible meniscus region, due to which there is almost no difference between the fits made using the arc and Carroll's equations. Using an ellipse to approximate the profile would lead to a large error. A circular arc has been used, in this case, to generate a quarter model of the droplet.

The fibre was modeled as transversely isotropic, with a longitudinal modulus of 45 GPa. The corresponding transverse and shear modulus values were calculated using the ASM2 model with a CMF V_f of 0.6. A 3 μm thick layer was used to represent the interphase. The properties of this region were calculated using the exponential, linear and reciprocal laws, and the values at 1.5 μm from the fibre surface were used throughout the entire thickness of the layer. Three different vice positions

were used, corresponding to vice angles (Fig. 2) of 6.36° , 18.97° and 36.43° .

It was observed that although the stresses and strains in the interphase were highest at the beginning of loading, the stress distribution is altered after local yielding at the contact region between the vice and the matrix. With further loading, the interphase starts to get debonded from the bottom, and after the drop following peak load, there is still a portion of the interphase at the top of the droplet, binding the droplet to the fibre. At the end of a microbond test, it is commonly observed that a portion of the droplet remains on the fibre after passing in between the blades (Fig. 9a). In the simulations, after the peak load, a crack was initiated in the droplet in the region between the droplet-vice contact area and the fibre (Fig. 9b). The intact portion of the interphase was present above this crack. The simulation thus indicates that the crack could potentially grow and divide the droplet into two, with a small portion close to the top and the majority below the crack, as observed in the experiments.

Among the simulations using different interphase properties and vice angles, the closest agreement with experimental load-extension behaviour was obtained with the 6.36° vice angle and the interphase properties calculated using the reciprocal law (Fig. 10c). For the different vice angles used, it was noticed that when the blades were far from the fibre, higher stresses were generated at the interphase for the same fibre load, as compared to the stresses generated when the blades were nearer. When the properties calculated with the reciprocal law were assigned to the interface, with the vice angle being 6.36° , the predicted peak load of 0.125 N was within 20% of the experimental peak load of 0.156 N for specimen 3.

4.3 Impregnated yarn failure

4.3.1 Tested strength and stiffness

A knee area at the beginning of the loading history for all yarns can be noticed due to the absence of any preload before beginning the test.

In the stress-strain plot for the impregnated flax/epoxy yarns (Fig. 11), it is to be noted that although the yarns by themselves demonstrate a large scatter in properties, the scatter is greatly

reduced when impregnated with epoxy. The average modulus is 1.78 GPa (± 0.17), and the average ultimate strength is 109.8 MPa (± 3.5).

The low scatter is due to the role of the matrix in acting as a cohesive layer holding the fibres together, and enabling redistribution of stresses upon failure of some fibres. In this aspect, these impregnated yarns can be considered to be composites in themselves.

4.3.2 Yarn failure simulation

In the interphase layers surrounding the fibres in the impregnated yarns, it can be observed that damage develops and propagates both in the radial and axial directions (Fig. 12). As for the fibres themselves, the weakest fibres failed first, followed by a redistribution of load, with the strongest fibres carrying the load.

Reasonably good agreement with experimental stiffness and strength was observed (Fig. 13). The numerically obtained stiffness was within three standard deviations of the experimentally obtained average of 1.78 GPa. The strength predictions were within 10% of the experimentally obtained average value of 109.8 MPa.

5. Conclusions

A hierarchical framework to obtain composite macro-scale properties from properties on the micro-scale is proposed. In this paper, the framework is used to estimate the properties of impregnated yarns from the properties of single fibres and the interphase region.

Single flax fibres are considered as analogous to cylindrical composite tubes, and their longitudinal and transverse moduli estimated by using the CLT theory and varying the microfibril helix angles. Using a range of MFA values determined experimentally, the longitudinal moduli predicted by the CLT models lie within the range of properties displayed by 93% of tested fibres.

Numerical simulation of a microbond test performed to investigate failure of the interphase region between the fibre and matrix showed good agreement with the experimental failure behavior, both in a quantitative and qualitative manner. It was discovered that after the drop following peak load, a portion of the interphase remains intact at the top of the droplet. This is possibly responsible for the small

part of the droplet remaining bonded to the fibre, as commonly observed in micrographs of specimens after complete debonding. The value predicted by the simulation is within 20% of the experimental result.

Single fibre and interphase properties are used in an FE model of of impregnated yarn failure. Fibre properties as represented by the Weibull distributions (Fig. 4), and interphase properties used in the microbond simulations are used. Strengths predicted by the FE model are within 10% of experimental results.

We have numerically modelled the elastic and damaged mechanical behaviour of the fibre and interphase regions in matrix-impregnated yarns. Our methodology can be used to analyze the properties of full natural fibre composites, and to estimate their design strengths.

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Fig. 1. Structure of natural fibres

Fig. 2. Test configuration for a microbond test - l is embedded length of the fibre, h is height of the droplet, and ϕ is the vice angle

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3. Weibull plots of a) fibre strength values, and b) fibre modulus values

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. Histogram of SFTT data and overlaid Weibull fits

Fig. 5. FE mesh of the yarn with matrix, fibres and interface (dark regions around fibres)

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6. Modulus of S2 layer predicted by the analytical model

Specimen	Nominal IFSS [MPa]	Frictional shear stress [MPa]
1	7.45	4.65
2	4.85	3.68
3	5.53	2.5
4	5.75	4.5

Fig. 7. Results from microbond tests: i) load-extension behavior (chart above), and ii) nominal and frictional stresses calculated by analytical models

Fig. 8. Profile of microbond specimen 3, and fits made to its profile using Carroll's equations, arc shape and ellipse shapes

(a)

(b)

Fig. 9. a) Matrix remaining on the fibre at the end of a microbond test [19], and b) indication of similar behaviour from our simulations

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 10. Results from microbond simulations for three different vice angles, with interphase properties calculated using a) exponential law, b) linear law, and c) reciprocal law

Fig. 11. Stress-strain data from tests of impregnated flax/epoxy yarns

Fig. 12. Progression of damage due to shear in the interface region of the fibres. The areas in black are the most severely damaged

Fig. 13. Comparison of the stress-strain behavior of impregnated yarns predicted from the numerical model with that obtained from the experiments

Table 1. Properties of Prime20 resin, as supplied by manufacturer

Tensile modulus [GPa]	Tensile strength [MPa]	Cured density [g/cm^3]
3.5	37	1.144

Table 2. Relative thicknesses or volume fractions (V_f) of the four layers in flax fibres, as proposed by i) Astley, and ii) Gassan

Model	CML	S_1	S_2	S_3
Astley (ASM1)	0.19	0.13	0.6	0.09
Gassan (ASM2)	0.08	0.08	0.76	0.08

Table 3. Properties of S_2 layer for different volume fractions

Property	$V_f=0.55$	$V_f=0.6$	$V_f=0.65$	$V_f=0.7$
E_{11} [GPa]	75.30	81.90	88.50	95.10
E_{22} [GPa]	16.14	17.40	18.66	19.92
G_{12} [GPa]	2.89	3.08	3.27	3.46
ν_{12}	0.15	0.15	0.14	0.13

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